

Long-read genomic sequencing of *Bacillus velezensis* sub-clones selected for differential protease activities

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Abstract

A *Bacillus velezensis* strain was isolated as a contaminant on an SM plate exhibiting a large hydrolysis halo of skimmed milk casein. After sub-culturing, several phenotypic sub-clones were isolated and characterized by colony appearance and the size of the hydrolysis halo. We performed genome sequencing using Illumina and Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) platforms to generate hybrid assemblies of four sub-clones based on their extracellular protease activities. These data will enable further exploration of the genetic basis underlying differences in protease activity in *Bacillus velezensis*, an important phenotypic trait with significant bio-industrial applications.

Introduction

The bacterial genus *Bacillus spp.*, in particular *Bacillus velezensis*, is widely known and studied for its important enzymatic capabilities such as proteases (Harwood et al., 2022; Lageiro et al., 2025; Fergany et al., 2026), its bio-control capabilities as a plant growth-promoting bacterium (PGPB) (Yu et al., 2024; Kenfaoui et al., 2024;Zhu et al., 2025) and its ability to produce several biomolecules such as fungicides, surfactants, antioxidants, lipopeptides etc (Ali et al., 2022; Ji et al., 2025). We isolated a strain of *Bacillus velezensis* as a contaminant on a Petri dish containing skimmed milk (SM), commonly used as a substrate for detecting protease activity. Because this

contaminant exhibited a much larger hydrolysis halo than the fungal strains we typically use, we decided to investigate it. We quickly observed that this bacterium is highly unstable and produces colonies with very different phenotypes on SM and LB media. Two main phenotypes stand out, with a near-constant correlation between the appearance on the dish and protease production capacity: a whitish appearance associated with low protease capacity and a dull appearance associated with high protease capacity. White sectors often appear on the dull colonies, indicating genetic instability rather than contamination (Darmon and Leach, 2014). We therefore undertook genome sequencing of these variants. With the support of GetGenome (Canham et al. 2024), we initially sequenced five variants using Illumina technology and later sequenced four variants—two of each phenotype—using the Oxford Nanopore platform to generate long-read sequences.

Material and Methods

Bacterial isolates and sub-clones

The first bacterium isolated was a contaminant on an SM plate exhibiting a large hydrolysis halo of skimmed milk casein. After sub-culturing on SM plates, phenotypic variants were isolated and characterized by colony appearance and hydrolysis halo size.

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

Illumina sequencing

Isolates were initially sequenced using Illumina technology and named 1301 to 1305, each selected based on exhibiting diverse proteolytic capabilities and phenotypes (Table 1A). Subclone 1304, identified as *B. stercoris*, was likely a contaminant isolated incidentally.

Cells were cultured to an equivalent OD600 of 10 or ~40mg wet weight and resuspended in a tube with DNA/RNA Shield (Zymo Research, USA). DNA extraction, sequencing and genome assembly were performed by MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK), following its protocols available at <https://microbesng.com/>. Briefly, cell suspension were lysed with TE buffer containing lysozyme (MPBio, USA) metapolyzyme (Sigma Aldrich, USA) and RNase A (ITW Reagents, Spain), incubated for 25 min at 37°C. Proteinase K (VWR Chemicals, Ohio, USA) (final concentration 0.1mg/mL) and SDS (Sigma-Aldrich, Missouri, USA) (final concentration 0.5% v/v) were added and incubated for 5 min at 65°C. Genomic DNA was purified using an equal

volume of SPRI beads and resuspended in EB buffer (10mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0). DNA was quantified with the Quant-iT dsDNA HS kit (ThermoFisher Scientific). Libraries for sequencing were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol with the following modifications: input DNA was increased 2-fold, and PCR elongation time was increased to 45 seconds. Libraries were sequenced using the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 platform (Illumina, San Diego, USA) and a 250 bp paired-end protocol. The resulting sequences were processed using Trimmomatic version 0.39 (Bolger et al., 2014), with a Q15 quality threshold per sliding window, and assembled using SPAdes v3.7 (Bankevich et al. 2012). Quality assessment was performed using a combination of in-house scripts and the software Samtools version 1.4 ([git://github.com/samtools/samtools.git](https://github.com/samtools/samtools.git)), BedTools version 2.18 (Quinlan and Hall, 2010), bwa-mem (Li and Durbin, 2009) and Quast version 5.0.2 (Gurevich et al., 2013). Subsequently, assemblies were annotated using the NCBI Prokaryotic Genome Annotation Pipeline (PGAP). Assembly statistics were obtained from the NCBI submission portal.

Long-read sequencing using Oxford-Nanopore Technologies(ONT)

Strains were next subjected to Illumina and ONT sequencing to produce improved genome assemblies and to capture non-chromosomal genetic elements. Illumina sequencing was performed as above.

Long-read genomic DNA libraries were prepared by MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK) using the Oxford Nanopore SQK-LSK109 ligation sequencing kit with Native Barcoding Expansion EXP-NBD104/114, using 400–500 ng of high-molecular-weight genomic DNA. Barcoded samples were pooled and sequenced on a GridION device using FLO-MIN106 (R9.4.1) or FLO-MIN111 (R10.3) flow cells. ONT reads were base-called and de-multiplexed using Dorado with the dna_r10.4.1_e8.2_400bps_sup model (model version v4.3.0). Hybrid genome assemblies were generated using Unicycler v0.4.0, incorporating both Illumina and ONT reads. Genome assemblies were annotated using the NCBI Prokaryotic Genome Annotation Pipeline (PGAP). Assembly statistics were obtained from the NCBI submission portal.

Results

All sequence data is available from NCBI/GenBank under the BioProject: [PRJNA1034616](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA1034616).

We initially selected five isolates based on their differential protease activities on solid media for Illumina short-read sequencing (Table 1A). In a follow-up study, we selected four sub-clones, two (20001 and 20002) as weakly producing protease sub-clones and two (20003 and 20004) as strong producers to generate hybrid sequences using both Illumina and ONT sequencing (Table 1B).

This study will allow us to explore the genetic basis for the observed difference between our two types of phenotypic sub-clones and will likely reveal important genetic elements underpinning other important phenotypes commonly observed in *Bacillus velezensis* strains.

Table 1: Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA: A-First sequencing series using Illumina platform performed in 2023; B- Second series: long read-sequencing using Oxford-Nanopore platform, performed in 2026.

A- The Illumina assemblies for 2023 sub-clones:

Feature	Value	Value	Value	Value
Strain name	A3	1302	Bam 1	C3
Species assignment	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>
GenBank accession	GCA_033903305.1 (replaced)	GCA_033949505.1 (replaced)	GCA_033952365.1 (replaced)	GCA_033952305.1 (replaced)
Genome size	4.1 Mb	4.1 Mb	4.1 Mb	4.1 Mb
Number of contigs	30	42	35	37
Contig N50	1 Mb	1 Mb	1 Mb	1 Mb
GC content	46.5	46.5%	46.5%	46.5%
Sequencing coverage	82X	90X	117X	73X
Number of genes	4,121	4,127	4,148	4,148
Protein-coding sequences (CDS)	3,941	3,948	3,964	3,964
Closest reference genome	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>
BioProject	PRJNA1034616	PRJNA1034616	PRJNA1034616	PRJNA1034616
BioSample	SAMN38062993	SAMN38080784	SAMN38081128	SAMN38082403
SUBID	SUB13971712	SUB13984670	SUB13984809	SUB13986349
Assembly level	Contig	Contig	Contig	Contig

B- The Illumina and Oxford Nanopore hybrid assembly for 2026 sub-clones:

Feature	Value	Value	Value	Value
Strain name*	20001 (A3)	20002 (1302)	20003 (Bam1)	20004 (C3)
Species assignment	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>
GenBank accession	GCA_033903305.2	GCA_033949505.2	GCA_033952365.2	GCA_033952305.2
Genome size	4.1 Mb	4.1 Mb	4.1 Mb	4.1 Mb
Number of contigs	2	2	2	2
Contig N50	4.1 Mb	4.1 Mb	4.1Mb	4.1 Mb
GC content	46.5%	46.5%	46.5%	46.5%
Sequencing coverage	45.25X	45.44X	44.57%	52.17X
Number of genes	4,122	4,121	4,148	4,147
Protein-coding sequences (CDS)	3,928	3,928	3,947	3,949
ANI to closest reference	97.71%	97.71%	97.7%	97.7%
Closest reference genome	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>
BioProject	PRJNA1034616	PRJNA1034616	PRJNA1034616	PRJNA1034616
BioSample	SAMN38062993	SAMN38080784	SAMN38081128	SAMN38082403
SUBID	SUB15985576	SUB15994000	SUB15993916	SUB15994005
Assemblylevel	Complete Genome	Complete Genome	Complete Genome	Complete Genome

* In strain name, in addition to the actual names of the sub-clones (20001-20004), we have included in parentheses the names given by NCBI/GenBank.

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